

ESiIL Collaboration Lead Guidelines and Resources

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In this packet are three resources for leads of working groups when creating group norms and forming collaboration plans. We have also included an AI/ML scoreboard tracker to help teams track their AI use and application.

- ESIIL Working Group Norms and Collaboration Plan Firestarter Questions
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ESIIL Working Group Norms and Collaboration Plan Firestarter Questions

The following set of questions are to help teams navigate discussions around norms and collaboration in a structured manner. These are not all the questions a team may need to consider and some of these questions may not relate to all teams. As a result, these “firestarter” questions, can help grease the wheel on collaboration discussions.

This set of questions comes from a previous ESIIL team science training that team members can see the presentation and recording of on Zenodo if of interest. These are listed at the end of the questions.

Please keep in mind that these questions are not a checklist. Your group should assess which of these questions are most relevant to your particular team and your team’s goals. We strongly recommend that PIs and leads review these types of questions prior to a team convening. There is also a fillable collaboration plan that groups can use that cover some of the topics but not all of them. If you have any questions about making your team’s collaboration plan, or want help through a guided facilitation, please contact the ESIIL Team Science and Community Care Team: Kayleigh Ward at kayleigh.ward@colorado.edu and Susan Sullivan at susan.sullivan@colorado.edu.

Firestarter categories and sample questions

A. Shared Vision and Purpose

- How does each team member define success for this project?
- What does shared success look like for the team as a whole?
- Beyond this grant or project, what (if anything) do we want this collaboration to enable?

B. Roles, Responsibilities, and Participation

- What does each team member contribute to the collaboration?
- Where do roles overlap, and where are they distinct?
- What decision-making authority does each role carry?
- What needs or constraints (time, access, resources) may affect participation?

C. Decision-Making and Power

- What types of decisions will this team need to make?
- How will routine decisions be made?

- How will high-stakes or contested decisions be handled?
- When does the PI decide independently, and when does the group decide collectively?

D. Communication and Coordination

- How often will the team meet, and in what formats?
- What communication tools will be used for day-to-day coordination?
- What are expectations for responsiveness and follow-through?
- How will information, decisions, and changes be documented?

E. Credit, Recognition, and Authorship

- What types of products are anticipated from this work?
- How will decisions about authorship and credit be made?
- How will contributions that are not captured by publications be recognized?

F. Conflict and Repair

- What kinds of tensions or conflicts are most likely to arise in this collaboration?
- How will concerns be raised safely?
- What steps will the team take if conflict escalates?
- When, if ever, will outside facilitation or mediation be used?

G. Reflection and Adaptation

- How will the team know if collaboration is working well?
- What signals indicate that something needs attention?
- How often will the team revisit the collaboration plan? When new members join? Every 6 months?

Related slides: Ward, K. (2026, January 27). ESIIL Team Science Workshop: Collaboration Plans Beyond the Proposal—Coordinating Communication, Care, and Collective Work. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20433503>

Related recording: Ward, K. (2026, January 27). [Video] ESIIL Team Science Workshop: Collaboration Plans Beyond the Proposal—Coordinating Communication, Care, and Collective Work. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20433669>

ESIIL Working Group Norms and Collaboration Plan Fillable

The following is a fillable outline of a potential team collaboration plan that represents the different pieces a working group would need to address to effectively, respectfully and productively work together. The categories include values related to 1) interpersonal dynamics, 2) logistical commitments 3) technical commitments and 4) data sharing. While this is a template, this is not *the template*. **You should** add and delete items as appropriate to your working group (such as different sections, items, or others).

Once your team has completed this type of document it makes it much easier to integrate new team members as they can identify whether they align with the group's norms and commitments. Similarly, if group conflict does arise, the team can refer back to this agreement. If continued unproductive conflict continues, the contract provides a professional way to address such behavior.

Interpersonal Dynamics

The items under this category should facilitate your team members being excited, safe and having an easy time working together. For any item you add or delete make sure to reflect as a group as to what this value means in *practice*. For example, how team members want to work with and treat one another while collaborating. Specifying these helps the team name the values, behaviors, and expectations that create a healthy working environment, such as honesty, respect, trust, inclusion, psychological safety, accountability, and openness to feedback. **Use this space to identify what matters most in how the team communicates, handles disagreement, supports one another, and builds shared trust. Make sure to check in with your Collaboration Lead.**

Honesty

- What does honesty mean to the group? For example, it could be about communicating what's working and what isn't, work loads, issues with data, etc.

Respect and patience

- What does respect mean to the group? Are there different ways to convey respect that would be appreciated by the group?

Being proactive and taking initiative

- What does it mean to be proactive and taking initiative in each other's work?

Being self-aware

- What does being self-aware mean to the team? For example, this could be related to speaking time, frequency speaking, number of leadership tasks held by one person, etc.

Identity and differences

- How does the group want to honor the difference of their different team members? For example, not all teams come from the same discipline, nor do all team members speak the same language, come from the same culture, or have the same training.

Listening

- What does listening to each other mean? Will the group be comfortable with people multitasking while others are presenting? How about attendance at meetings?

Honoring each other's time

- How will the group ensure that everyone's time is used most effectively? If someone is falling behind on a task, does the group have measures in place to support each other, and shift around group time and resources?
- Is group time going to be a review of team work or a space for discussing issues of the work done so far?

Logistical Commitments

Logistical commitments are the practical agreements that help the team collaborate smoothly and reliably. You can think of these like interlocking gears with interpersonal dynamics and technical commitments. The items listed below, help the team clarify expectations around meeting schedules, attendance, communication channels, response times, deadlines, roles, decision-making processes, and follow-through. **Use this space to identify what the team needs in order to stay organized, coordinate effectively, and respect one another's time and capacity.**

Check-ins and standing meetings

- How often does the larger group plan to meet?
- How often do smaller specific task related groups plan to meet? In what modality?
- Will meetings be recorded? Will there be a notetaker to add meeting minutes to a shared google drive, repo, etc?
- How will the group accommodate different timezones if meeting online?

Deadlines

- How will the team set deadlines for different things? For example, when are team members expected to respond to emails by? When are work tasks to be completed? How

will those be tracked, documented and communicated to the group? *Who* is setting deadlines? Is this a group decision or a PI decision?

- By when do team members need to communicate to the group that they will not be able to meet a deadline? How will the team address these needs?
- Where will you track deadlines? Google sheets? Monday? Asana? Github?

Emails and Slack

- How will the group primarily communicate with each other? Will there be a primary email thread or will the team work in slack? How should work updates be provided?

In-person meetings

- What does the group need to prepare or be ready for prior to an in person meeting? Will team members need to review each other's work? Will the PIs or other leads be responsible for an agenda?

Technical Commitments

Technical commitments are related to the tools, systems, standards, and technical practices (or software) the team agrees to use during the collaboration. The following list of items can help the team clarify expectations around shared platforms, file organization, version control, documentation, accessibility, troubleshooting, security practices, and technical responsibilities. **Use this space to identify how the team will maintain consistency, quality, and ease of use across its shared work. Make sure to check in with your Tech Lead.**

Shared Group Folder Management

- What system does the team want to keep works in progress? Who will have file ownership? When is it allowable for someone to delete or add something to the shared folder management system? How will you track changes to the work (e.g., track changes in documents, well detailed commit messages for coding, etc).
- How will you name folders, documents, datasets, etc., such that everyone in the group can easily navigate things?
- How often does the team need to update items? For example, if a task is due in 3 months, does the team expect everything uploaded at once, or to see changes uploaded over time?
- How will the team use their folder management system to ensure group transparency and foster team members keeping progress with each other's work?

Collaborative Work Products

- For any collaborative products, how do you want to co-work? Sharing files over sharepoint? Dropbox? Google docs or sheets?
- How will these smaller teams of the group track their work and make to do lists?
- Who is responsible for each collaborative product?
- Where will you keep references updated? Zotero? Mendeley?
- Are other group members not on that particular collaborative product allowed to edit or only view these products?
- For code, will the entire team be added to the GitHub repository? Or just the related collaborators from the team?

Data Sharing, Management and Attribution

For this section on data sharing, this is generally related to how the team will share, access, manage, protect, and use data throughout the collaboration. It helps the team clarify expectations around data ownership, permissions, confidentiality, appropriate use, attribution, and timelines for sharing. **Use this space to identify what data will be shared, with whom, under what conditions, and how the team will ensure responsible and transparent data practices.**

Sharing Work Products & Data

- Will in progress works be shared outside the group?
- When sharing products does the whole team need to be notified or just the PI?
- Are only completed products or datasets allowed to be shared?
- Does the team only want products that have been published shared outside the group?
- If those outside the team are given products, who do those “outsiders” look like? A tenure committee? A co-worker/lab-mate? A community partner? Industry?
- What license will be put on works? (Creative Commons? MIT (code repositories)? etc).

Attribution

- For completed products, how will the team track contributions? Using the ESIL CRediT sheet? Some other form? What is a contribution that is “counted” towards authorship?

Transparency

- How will the team ensure the different versions of datasets and papers are preserved?

- How will track and disclose, if relevant, any AI use to team members and publishers?
Using the ESIL AI Scoreboard?

ESIL Working Group Norms and Collaboration Plan Example

The following is an example of a filled out collaboration plan that includes categories related to how the group will treat each other (e.g., interpersonal dynamics), how they will communication broadly and meet any deadlines (e.g., logistic commitments), and how they will organize their work (e.g., technical commitments).

This is an example of how you might fillout the fillable version of this template. While viewing this example, keep in mind that **while this may have worked for another group, you should adapt this example to the unique values, experiences, personal and work needs of your particular team (and also your software)**. Please treat this example as a further jumpstarter for thinking about and writing down your team agreements (e.g., adding new categories, new values, etc).

Once your team has completed this type of document it makes it much easier to integrate new team members as they can identify whether they align with the group's norms and commitments. Similarly, if group conflict does arise, the team can refer back to this agreement. If continued unproductive conflict continues, the plan provides a professional way to address such behavior.

Interpersonal Dynamics

We will follow these guidelines to work towards the goal of creating a community/team where people feel excited to work together and comfortable asking for help.

Honesty

We will be honest with the group about our limitations and capacity to complete tasks. We will also commit to putting in the work and time that the project requires.

Respect and patience

We will assume the good intentions of our team members while taking responsibility for the impact we have on others. When issues arise, we will communicate respectfully and directly (use "I" statements). We will respect and actively listen to all ideas from every team member.

Being proactive and taking initiative

We will take responsibility for being familiar with other elements of the project (note: this does not mean we will all become experts in every component, but simply that we will put in work to

understand each component well enough to see the connections between the different components) and with the ESIL process.

Being self-aware

We will be aware of how much space we take up in group settings (on calls and in meetings). A useful tool is to stop and ask ourselves, “Why am I talking?” before speaking up, to be sure that our contribution is useful and relevant.

Identity and differences

As a diverse group, we will honor gender, cultural, and disciplinary differences. In particular, we will be aware of each other’s expertise (e.g. not explain someone’s field to them), gender dynamics (e.g. who is taking on different types of work), and how other forms of privilege (e.g. nationality and linguistic) affect the group.

Listening

We will listen to each other sincerely and respectfully, recognizing that there are many different communication styles, both verbal and non-verbal.

Honoring each other’s time

We are all busy people, so we will be respectful of each other’s time. For example, we won’t show up late to calls or multitask during calls and we will meet group deadlines so that interdependent tasks can move forward as planned.

Logistical Commitments

Check-ins

- Every three months, two people will be in charge of facilitating an anonymous survey to check in on how everyone in the group is doing (regarding group dynamics, workload, etc) and reporting the results back to the group. We will rotate this care work between team members.
- As part of these check-ins, we will report an estimated amount of time that we have spent on our components of the project, so we can get a sense of whether some people are investing significantly more time than others and rebalance the workload moving forward. This time accounting will not be geared towards guilt-tripping people into feeling like they should work more, but rather towards making sure that no one is feeling overburdened and that everyone is feeling engaged and supported.

Deadlines

- We will set clear and achievable goals.

- We will meet deadlines set by the team. If we cannot make a deadline (because sometimes life gets in the way), we will let the team know as soon as possible. We will be honest about when we've taken on too much and need help.
- We will use Asana to manage team deadlines and intermediate personal deadlines.

Emails and Slack

- We will primarily use Slack to communicate about the project.
- We will post bi-weekly updates on Slack to report on our progress. This will free up standing meetings to be more focused on things that we need to discuss as a group, rather than simply reporting on what we have done.
- We will be prompt in answering emails and Slack messages from teammates.

Standing meetings

- We will let the group know beforehand if we can't make a standing meeting and commit to reviewing the notes from the meeting and following up via Slack if we have questions or clarifications.

In-person meetings

- We will commit to getting preparatory work done before in-person meetings so we don't waste precious face-to-face time.

Technical Commitments

Shared Group Folder Management

- Keep all data in shared data folders
- Do not delete data from shared folders unless it has been agreed upon by all
- Will not share data in folders with others unless everyone in the group agrees
- Follow common file naming system
- Keep data current (as much as possible based on internet availability) in the shared Drive

Track Methodological Progress

- Keep shared notes on all data processing
- Add comments to code so everyone on the team (and our future selves) knows what's going on

- Document the references/sources and reasons for including them

Collaborative Work Products

- Use shared google docs for documents
- Use Asana to make and track to-do lists
- Use Slack to communicate between group members
- Keep references up-to-date in Zotero
- Code will be made editable to those directly working on it, but shared freely with other team members to view and comment on
- Use platforms such as Github (for algorithm programming) or Bitbucket (for group file repository) in order to have multiple-collaborative coding sites.
- Document methodological decisions as we go in Google Docs

Sharing Work Products & Data

- Ask for permission from the team before sharing results/analyses with others besides meetings with advisors and informal lab presentations/office conversations.